

Special Needs Education

Country Data

2008

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education

This document has been produced and published by the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education. Extracts from the document are permitted provided a clear reference to the source is given.

This document has been edited by Amanda Watkins (Agency Staff Member) on the basis of contributions from Representative Board members and National Co-ordinators of Agency member and observer countries. All of their contact details can be found on the Country Information Pages of the Agency's website: <http://www.european-agency.org/country-information>

More information regarding the systems of special needs education in Agency member countries is available from the National Overviews section of the Agency website: <http://www.european-agency.org/country-information>

ISBN: 978-87-92387-47-9 (Electronic)

ISBN: 978-87-92387-46-2 (Printed)

2009

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education

Secretariat
Østre Stationsvej 33
DK-5000 Odense C Denmark
Tel: +45 64 41 00 20
secretariat@european-agency.org

Brussels Office
3 Avenue Palmerston
BE-1000 Brussels Belgium
Tel: +32 2 280 33 59
brussels.office@european-agency.org

www.european-agency.org

Education and Culture DG

Lifelong Learning Programme

The production of this document has been supported by the DG Education, Training, Culture and Multilingualism of the European Commission: http://europa.eu.int/comm/dgs/education_culture/index_en.htm

CONTENTS

Preamble.....7

AUSTRIA.....8

BELGIUM (FLEMISH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)..... 11

BELGIUM (FRENCH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)..... 13

BULGARIA..... 15

CYPRUS..... 18

CZECH REPUBLIC.....20

DENMARK.....22

ESTONIA.....24

FINLAND.....26

FRANCE.....28

GERMANY.....30

GREECE.....32

HUNGARY.....35

ICELAND	37
IRELAND	41
ITALY	43
LATVIA	46
LITHUANIA	48
LUXEMBOURG	50
MALTA	52
NETHERLANDS	54
NORWAY	56
POLAND	58
PORTUGAL	60
SLOVENIA	62
SPAIN	64
SWEDEN	66
SWITZERLAND	68

UNITED KINGDOM (ENGLAND)	70
UNITED KINGDOM (SCOTLAND)	74
UNITED KINGDOM (WALES)	76

Preamble

The Agency SNE data collection is a biennial exercise with data provided by the Representatives of the Agency. In all cases this data is from official Ministerial sources.

All data refers to pupils officially identified as having SEN as defined in the country in question and all the data presented in this document has been collected in line with each country's own legal definition of SEN. These definitions are also provided in the texts.

Data provided by countries covers eight agreed questions – five are statistical:

1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN).
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings).
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools.
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools.
5. Pupils with SEN in inclusive settings.

(NB: Segregation refers to education where the pupil with special needs follows education in separate special classes or special schools for the largest part – 80% or more – of the school day.)

The information submitted is raw data i.e. actual numbers of pupils registered in different settings.

The three remaining questions provide contextual information with notes and clarifications, particularly referring to legal definitions of special needs:

6. Compulsory age range with a specification of primary and secondary age phases if appropriate.
7. Clarification of public and private sector education.
8. The legal definition of SEN in the country.

Data was collected in late 2008, but sources used are from the academic years 2006/2007 or 2007/2008.

The following notations are used throughout the document:

* Indicates an associated note.

0 Indicates zero and not missing data.

- Indicates no data available.

AUSTRIA

Question	Data				Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	774,199		63,029			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	837,228	2006/2007
	329,161	445,038	18,088	44,941		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	26,822		831			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	27,653 *	2006/2007
	9,390	17,432	269	562		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	9,736		459			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	10,195	2006/2007
	2,772	6,964	142	317		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,039 *		98			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,137	2006/2007

Source: Statistics Austria.
Detailed statistical information for Austria is available from:
http://www.statistik.at/web_de/statistiken/bildung_und_kultur/index.html
Note: The total number of pupils in secondary level is higher than in previous years, because this table includes also pupils in academic secondary schools. This type of school is also compulsory up to the 9th level, but the numbers were not included in previous data collection exercises.

Source: Statistics Austria.
* No data is available regarding pupils with sensory or physical disabilities in academic secondary schools and vocational schools, as they are not labelled as having SEN in these schools.

Source: Statistics Austria.

Source: Statistics Austria.
* 827 pupils are enrolled in special classes including the primary and secondary level. These pupils are counted under the primary level. These figures are for pupils with SEN in primary, secondary and prevocational schools up to the ninth compulsory school year.
See note * for question 2 above.

	1,076	963	25	73	2,137	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Austria. These figures are for pupils with SEN in primary, secondary and prevocational schools up to the ninth compulsory school year. See note * for question 2 above.
	15,047		274				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	5,542	9,505	102	172	15,321	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	9 years of compulsory education (age 6 to 15). Primary and secondary phase age ranges are as follows – primary level: 1 st to 4 th grade; secondary level: 5 th to 9 th grade.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public schools are either financed: completely by the federal state (teacher salaries, maintenance of school buildings) in terms of academic secondary schools, higher vocational schools, teacher training colleges etc.; or financed by the federal state (teacher salaries) and the communities (school maintenance) in terms of compulsory schools (primary, lower secondary, special or prevocational schools); or by the federal state (teacher salaries) and a federal province (school maintenance) e.g. vocational schools. Private schools – the majority of private schools are (officially recognised) denominational schools and they are maintained by the respective church. The federal state is obliged to finance teacher salaries. Private associations who are in favour of a special pedagogy ('reform pedagogy' like 'Waldorf' etc.) and who develop a particular curriculum that is not in line with the national curriculum are totally financed by their stakeholders. In case they fulfil certain given criteria they might get financial support by the state authorities as well. If private schools follow the national curriculum they may be given the mandate by the Ministry of Education to provide legal state certification (private schools with 'public law status').						

8. Legal Definition of SEN

A child is recognised as having special educational needs if – as a result of a physical or psychologically based disability – he/she is not able to achieve the goals of the national curriculum without receiving special provision. (§ 8, Compulsory Schooling Act Schulpflichtgesetz). The assessment procedure is carried out by the school district board upon the application of the parents, the head teacher of the school, or by the board itself with reference to expert opinions.

SEN provision is available for two 'categories' of pupils:

Category 1: Pupils with officially labelled special educational needs (pupils with physical and/or psychological disabilities) may either attend a special, or a mainstream school with additional support (based on parental choice).

Category 2: Pupils with special educational needs, but without certification (such as speech impediments, behaviour problems, visual or hearing impairments) are offered 'outpatient' provision by the Special Mobile Service in or outside classrooms.

The education of pupils with special educational needs is embedded in the general legislative framework for education such as:

The 1962 School Organisation Act (Schulorganisationsgesetz) is the foundation on which the current school organisation (including education of pupils with SEN in special schools (Sonderschulen) or mainstream settings) rests. The 'School Education Act' (Schulunterrichtsgesetz) is the legal framework for all issues concerning education within schools (e.g. assessment, enrolment of pupils, transition procedures within different types of schools etc.).

Special Needs Education in Austria: important milestones are the 15th Amendment to the 'School Organisation Act' of 1993, the 17th Amendment of 1996 and the associated amendments of the 'Compulsory Schooling Act' (Schulpflichtgesetz), the School Education Act and of the 'Basic Act on the Maintenance of Compulsory Schools' (Pflichtschulerhaltungs-Grundsatzgesetz). These amendments have re-oriented the educational system by providing new organisational and integrative forms of special pedagogical assistance for pupils with special educational needs in general compulsory schools (Allgemein bildende Pflichtschulen).

BELGIUM (FLEMISH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	268,442		610,582		879,024	2006/2007	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education. * Home education means that parents educate their children themselves, at home. Parents have to prove to the inspectorate that they can provide quality schooling.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	151,121	113,195	262,830	344,332			
		<i>In addition:</i> Part-time secondary: 3,460 * Home educated: 666		Part-time secondary: 3,420			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	51,122 *		*		51,122 *	2006/2007	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education. * It is not possible to tell which of these pupils are in private or public education. See note for question 1 above. ** In addition, 2,058 pupils are above compulsory school age (+18 years old) but it is not possible to say if they are in public or private education They are therefore counted in these figures.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	30,411	20,711 **	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	16,689		28,294		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	10,255	6,434	16,539	11,755	44,983	2006/2007	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* In the Flemish school system there are no special classes in mainstream schools. Pupils with SEN in mainstream schools are fully included.
	0		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	0	0	0	0	0 *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education. These pupils are included in mainstream classes for more than 80% of their school day. * It is not possible to tell which of these pupils are in private or public education.
	6,139 *		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,617 *	2,522	-	-	6,139	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	The age range covered by compulsory education is from 6 to 18 years old. Primary school: 6 to 12 years (compulsory). Secondary school: 12 to 18 years (compulsory).						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public education refers to community education and subsidised publicly run schools. Private sector refers to subsidised privately run schools. These are general catholic schools and they are financed by the government. The number of independent private schools is limited in the Flemish Community. Data on this type of school is not collected by the Department for Education and Training.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Special education is defined as: 'education, based on a pedagogical project that provides adapted schooling, care and therapy for pupils whose personal development cannot be or can insufficiently be guaranteed, temporarily or permanently, in an ordinary school. 8 types of special education are distinguished. The same categorisation is used for funding integrated education. Reference: Decree, 1997.						

BELGIUM (FRENCH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	686,168		- **		686,168	2007/2008	Source: Ministère de la Communauté Française AGERS-DGEO, rue Lavallée 1, 1080 Bruxelles. * For secondary mainstream and special schools, the data covers all the pupils registered in the secondary level including those past compulsory school age (i.e. older than 18 years). ** No data for any sectors – mainstream or special – is available for pupils in private education. See question 7.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	319,290	366,878 *	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	30,340		-		30,340	2007/2008	Source: Ministère de la Communauté Française. * The data covers pupils in the compulsory sector, but it is not possible to tell how many are above compulsory school age.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	15,277	15,063 *	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	30,203 *		-		30,203	2007/2008	Source: Ministère de la Communauté Française. * This number includes 45 pupils in non-permanent inclusion in mainstream schools: 44 in primary and 1 in the secondary level.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	15,226	14,977	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	-		-		-	-	Data is not available.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	137 *		-				Source: Ministère de la Communauté Française. * This number represents only pupils who are new to inclusive education for the reference year (2007/2008). Pupils in inclusive education from previous years are not included in these figures – they are enrolled in and therefore counted in mainstream school numbers.

	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	51	86	-	-	137	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The compulsory age phase is age 6 to 18 years. Primary school is from 6 to 12 and secondary from 12 to 18 years. In special schools, pupils can stay in the preschool to 8 years and in the primary school to 15, with special arrangements decided upon by the school council (the education team of the school, PMS centre and parents).</p>						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>The private sector receives no funding from the Community. They are obliged to follow the official programme that leads to the baccalaureate. Private schools make up a very small part of the education system; numbers are unknown.</p>						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The Decree of the 3 March 2004 organising special needs education gives the following definition in article 2 §1. Specialised education is reserved for children and adolescents who, on the basis of a multidisciplinary assessment conducted by defined institutions on basis of article 12, will benefit from an adapted education in relation to their special needs and pedagogical possibilities. These children and adolescents are called 'children and adolescents with special needs'. Specialised education is organised in 8 types. Each of them is an education adapted to the general and particular needs of children identified as having special educational needs. Specialised education is provided for pupils whose needs are of the same type, their needs defined in terms of the principal disability common to this group. For the pupils with multi disabilities, the type of specialised education is defined according to the educative needs that must be satisfied by priority according to the age and the possibilities of the person. The types of specialised education are: Type 1 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with light mental disabilities. Type 2 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with moderate or deep mental disabilities. Type 3 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with behaviour and personality deep problems. Type 4 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with physical problems. Type 5 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with illness or who are convalescing (classrooms in clinics or hospitals). Type 6 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with visual impairment. Type 7 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with auditory impairment. Type 8 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with instrumental impairment.</p>						

BULGARIA

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	693,270 *		- **		693,270	2006/2007	Source: National statistical institute. Ministry of Education and Science – regional inspectorates of education. * No separate data is available for pupils in primary and secondary sectors. A breakdown is number of pupils 6 to 15 years – 634,780; number of pupils aged 6 years in preparatory groups in the kindergartens – 58,490. ** All data for questions 1 to 5 relates to the public sector. There is no information on pupils with special educational needs in private schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	14,083 *		-		14,083	2007/2008 **	Source: Regional inspectorates of education. (See note at the foot of the table). * This data includes pupils from 7 to 18 years. ** Note more recent data is available relating to pupils with Special Educational Needs than the numbers of pupils in compulsory education overall.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	8,119		-		8,119	2007/2008	Source: Regional inspectorates of education. The number of special schools is: 3 – for children with hearing impairments; 2 – for children with visual impairments; 59 – for children with learning difficulties.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	391 *		-		391	2007/2008	Source: Regional inspectorates of education. * These pupils are in special classes in mainstream schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	5,573 *		-				Source: Regional inspectorates of education. * These pupils are supported by resource centres for inclusive education for pupils with special educational needs.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	-	-	-	-	5,573	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The Law for public education: Art. 7. (1) states that school education is up to 16 years of age is compulsory. (2) (amend. SG 36/98) states that school education starts in the year a child reaches 7 years of age. Children can go to the first class when they are 6 years old as long as their mental and physical development and their parents or their guardians permit this. Art. 20. (Amend., SG 90/02) (1) (amend. SG 36/98) states that the preparation of the children for school one year before their admission in the first class is obligatory and shall be implemented at the preparatory groups in the kindergartens or preparatory classes at the school - parents or the guardians are exempt from fees.</p> <p>School education is divided into basic (awarded after the completion of the basic level of education) and secondary (awarded after the completion of the upper secondary level of education). According to the education content it is general and vocational. On the basis of this principle schools are divided into general and vocational.</p> <p>The structure of school education is:</p> <p>Basic (single structure) education I to VIII grade. Primary school stage I to IV grade: 7 to 10 years. Lower secondary stage V to VIII grade: 11 to 14 years. Upper secondary education IX to XIII grade: 15 to 19 years. Upper secondary general education (with non-specialised and specialised schools). Vocational educational and training (incl. post-secondary education).</p> <p>Law for the public education: Art. 26. (amend. SG 36/98) (1) Schools within public education are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Elementary – from I to IV grade included; 2. Junior high schools – from V to VIII grade included; 3. Primary – from I to VIII grade included; 4. High schools – from IX to XII grade included; 5. Specialized high schools – from VIII to XII grade included; 6. High general education schools – from I to XII grade included; 7. (amend. SG 68/99) professional high schools – from VIII or IX to XII or XIII grade included; 8. (amend. SG 68/99) professional – from VII or VIII grade with a duration of education of up to three years, from IX grade – with a duration of education of up to four years, and professional colleges upon completed high school education – with a duration of education of up to two years; 9. Sports schools; 10. Fine arts schools; 11. Special schools; 12. (new – SG 41/06) for culture. 						

7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>Law for the public education: Art. 2. The system of the public education includes kindergartens, schools and servicing units.</p> <p>Art. 10. (amend. SG 36/98) (1) The kindergartens and the schools are state, municipal and private. The servicing units are state and municipal.</p> <p>(2) State education covers the kindergartens, the schools and the servicing units, which are of national importance and are financed by the state budget through the Ministry of Education and Science or by other ministries and departments. The properties, conceded to them for use, are public state ownership.</p> <p>(3) Municipal education covers the kindergartens, the schools and the servicing units, which are financed by the municipal budgets. The properties, conceded to them for use, are public municipal ownership.</p> <p>Private education is the kindergartens and the schools, which are opened or transformed upon a request by Bulgarian individuals and corporate bodies and are not financially maintained.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Regulation for implementation of the Law for the public education:</p> <p>Children and pupils with special educational needs are children and pupils with sensory, physical, multiple and mental disabilities, with learning difficulties and with speech-language disorders.</p> <p>The range of children with special educational needs is regulated legislatively in the Law for the public education (2002) and in the Regulation for implementation of the Law for the public education (2003).</p>

Note: In the regional structures of the Ministry of Education and Science – regional inspectorates of education, work with teams for complex pedagogical assessment, which consist of different specialists – special teachers, resource teachers, psychologists, speech therapists, teachers from kindergartens and schools, social workers etc., who conduct assessments of the children and pupils with disabilities. They direct them to certain kindergartens or schools as they recommended certain resources and assistance from different specialists from the kindergarten or the school in accordance with needs and abilities of children and pupils. In the country there are 28 (1 centre in the each region) resource centres for supporting the integrated education of children with special educational needs.

CYPRUS

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	107,326		13,651 *		120,977	2007/2008	Source: Ministry of Education and Culture, Annual Report. * No separate data is available for pupils in primary and secondary sectors.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	52,539	54,787	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	5,151		- *		5,151	2007/2008	Source: Special Education Department, Ministry of Education. * No data is available for pupils with special needs in the private sector. This applies to questions 2 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	2,895	2,256	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector *		Private Sector		276	2007/2008	Source: Special Education Department, Ministry of Education. * Special schools are all under the supervision of primary education, despite the age of the children attending.
	276		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		484	2007/2008	Source: Special Education Department, Ministry of Education.
	484		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		4,391	2007/2008	Source: Special Education Department, Ministry of Education.
	4,391		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	2,328	2,063	-	-	4,391	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	The age range is from 4.8 to 15 years old. Primary Education: 4.8 to 12 years old. Secondary Education: 12 to 15 years old.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public Sector: refers to the education provided by the State, free of charge. Private Sector: refers to the education that is provided by non-governmental institutions. These institutions are run by individuals after gaining license to work by the State.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	A child with special needs, according to the Law for Education and Training of Children with Special Needs 113(I)1999, means a child having a serious learning or special learning functioning or adjusting difficulty, caused by physical, mental or other general (unspecified) or psychological deficiencies and having need of special education and training. A child shall have a learning, special learning, functioning or adjusting difficulty if: - They have a seriously greater difficulty comparing with the majority of the children of the same age; or - They have a disability that excludes or hinders them from using the educational means of the sort the schools for children of the same age generally provide. Reference: Law for Education and Training of Children with Special Needs 113(I)19.						

CZECH REPUBLIC

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: IIE (Institute for Information on Education) database.
	872,074		15,926				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	451,981	420,093	6,065	9,861	888,000	2007/2008	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: IIE (Institute for Information on Education) database. * Data refers only to pupils in compulsory education and not solely to pupils of compulsory school age since due to their specific health conditions some compulsory school aged pupils continue their preschool education and start compulsory education later.
	73,695		2,673				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	32,479	41,216	1,404	1,269	76,368 *	2007/2008	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: IIE (Institute for Information on Education) database.
	29,478		1,770				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	12,869	16,609	957	813	31,248	2007/2008	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: IIE (Institute for Information on Education) database.
	8,831		130				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,678	5,153	55	75	8,961	2007/2008	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: IIE (Institute for Information on Education) database.
	35,386		773				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	15,932	19,454	392	381	36,159	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education is from 6 to 15 years. Primary education is from 6 to 11 years. Secondary education is from 12 to 15 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public sector – schools established by Ministries, municipalities or regions. Private sector – schools established by private bodies, church and/or denomination. All schools are entitled to the state contribution. Private schools are authorised to ask for tuition. Schools run by private bodies are funded by 60% of the particular funding formula designed for public schools. Under certain conditions such as a very good external evaluation done by the School Inspectorate, the funding of such a school may increase up to 100%. The funding of schools run by church/denomination is based on the same principles as public schools.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	A child/pupil/student with SEN is according to the law a child/pupil/student who is, or is likely to be, unable without the provisions of additional support to benefit from school education made generally for children/pupils/student of the same age. This is the group of pupils with special needs referred to in Question 2. The School Act specifies the group of children/pupils/students with special needs as follows: a) Children/pupils/students with impairment – physical, mental, sensory, speech and language impairment, specific learning and/or behavioural difficulties, autism and children with severe multiple needs. b) Children/pupils/students with health risk conditions. c) Children/pupils/students who are socially disadvantaged. The statistical data provided in this table does not cover children/pupils/students described in sections b) and c) above since for these groups no separate educational placement exists. To provide the picture about the mainstream/separate placement, the data in the table only covers pupils mentioned under letter a). These pupils have the right to be mainstreamed and/or educated at schools/classes organised for these children. References and sources of this information are: - The School act No. 561/2004; - Regulation on education of children, pupils, students with special needs and of gifted and talented children, pupils and students, No 73/2005.						

DENMARK

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	600,017 *		117,461 **		717,478	2006/2007	Source: Uni-C, Statistics Denmark, Ministry of Education. * 'Folkeskole' (Local schools) ** 'Fri Grundskole' (Private independent school) and 'Efterskole' (continuation school).
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	420,271	179,746	58,674	58,787			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	23,590		1,128		24,718 *	2006/2007	Source: Uni-C, Statistics Denmark, Ministry of Education. * The figure covers special needs education within all special classes. It is estimated that approximately 12% of all pupils have some form of special need, but data is not collected on all special needs in inclusive settings. Please see the note for question 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	14,056	9,534	613	515			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	5,393		- *		5,393	2006/2007	Source: Uni-C, Statistics Denmark, Ministry of Education. * No data is available for pupils in segregated special schools in the private sector.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,136	2,257	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	16,881		464				Source: Uni-C, Statistics Denmark, Ministry of Education. The majority of the pupils are in special classes situated in mainstream schools with the possibility of inclusion.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	10,029	6,852	154	310	17,345	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	<p>Source: Uni-C, Statistics Denmark, Ministry of Education.</p> <p>* Pupils with severe special needs fully integrated into mainstream classes.</p> <p>Apart from those pupils who are fully included in mainstream classes, there are extensive special needs education programmes. It is estimated that 22,000 – 23,500 pupils in the Danish Folkeskole receive support in or outside the classroom. Ref. 'Uddannelse – udvalgte nøgletal'. (Key data on education).</p>
	1,316		664				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	891	425	459	205	1,980 *	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory education commences on 1 of August in the calendar year of a pupil's 7th birthday and terminates on 31 July of the year, in which he or she has received regular instruction for 9 years, not including the pre-school class.</p> <p>Primary phase: age approximately 6 to 12 years (class 0 to 6).</p> <p>Secondary phase: age approximately 13 to 16 years (class 7 to 10).</p>						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>The 9 years of compulsory education do not necessarily have to be spent in a municipal Folkeskole. They may instead be spent in a private school. The State allocates grants to private schools – corresponding to approx. 80% of the total expenditure of the schools. The teaching in the private schools must be on a par with that of the Folkeskole. Around 12% of all Danish pupils attend a private school. This percentage does not include the so-called Efterskoler, continuation schools.</p>						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>SEN is defined as referring to people with severe physical and/or intellectual special needs (handicaps).</p> <p>Additional information: The teaching of children, young people and adults is regulated by a number of acts, and, with one exception (the act on special education for adults), the general provisions on special education are contained in the ordinary acts applying to the school area in question.</p> <p>In section 3 of the Act on the Folkeskole, it is laid down that 'Special education and other special educational assistance shall be given to pupils whose development requires special consideration or support', and it is directly mentioned that these provisions may contain deviations from the subject-range of the school, the provisions on proficiency assessment and the weekly timetable. (Additional information from the Danish National Overview 2004: www.european-agency.org).</p> <p>Reference: Ministry of Education, Denmark.</p>						

ESTONIA

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	124,806		3,093		127,899 *	2006/2007	Source: Estonian Educational Information System. * The data provide for questions 1 to 5 covers Primary – ISCED I – and secondary – ISCED II. ISCED III (upper secondary) is not covered in this data).
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	73,903	50,903	2,102	991			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	23,914		376		24,290 *	2006/2007	Source: Estonian Educational Information System. This shows all the pupils who receive learning support (e.g. IEP, speech therapy, remedial teaching etc) at all types of schools. * In addition there are 236 pupils with special educational needs above compulsory school age (i.e. older than 17) in compulsory settings across the public and private sectors.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	15,617	8,297	232	144			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	4,293		107		4,400 *	2006/2007	Source: Estonian Educational Information System. * In addition there are 157 pupils above compulsory school age (i.e. older than 17) in segregated special schools across the public and private sectors.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,938	2,355	52	55			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	1,725		11		1,736 *	2006/2007	Source: Estonian Educational Information System. * In addition there are 38 pupils above compulsory school age (i.e. older than 17) studying in special classes in mainstream schools in the public sector.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	511	1,214	11	0			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Estonian Educational Information System. This shows all the pupils who receive learning support (e.g. IEP, speech therapy, remedial teaching etc) in mainstream schools and mainstream classes. * In addition there are 41 pupils above compulsory school age (i.e. older than 17) in fully inclusive settings across the public and private sectors.

	17,896		258			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	13,168	4,728	169	89		
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory education begins in the first full school year after children have reached the age of 7. It continues until they have satisfactorily completed basic school, or reached the age of 17.</p> <p>However, the study period in special basic schools has been extended for pupils with physical disabilities, hearing and visual impairments; the basic school for them does not last 9 years, but 10 or even 11 years. Although, they are usually older than 17 (that is our compulsory school age) they are still acquiring basic education. Therefore there can be a form of contradiction between 'compulsory school age' and pupils achieving and receiving basic schooling.</p> <p>Primary phase age range is 7 to 13 years; lower secondary phase age range is 14 to 16 years.</p>					
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>Public schools are state and municipality schools. A private education institution is an educational institution based on the ownership of a legal person in private law and which shall operate pursuant to law, the legislation issued on the basis of law and the articles of association if the founder is a legal person in private law, and to its statute. (Private Education Institution Act § 2 (1). Passed on 3 June 1998).</p> <p>All schools (public and private schools) get money from the State for teachers' salary, in-service training and buying school-books.</p>					
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>In our Basic School and Upper Secondary School Act SEN has not been clearly defined. At present SEN has been stipulated as follows in the Basic School and Upper Secondary School Act § 4 15.09.1993:</p> <p>Depending on the need of pupils to receive special education, special support, intervention due to behavioural problems, or treatment, a basic school or an upper secondary school may be a school for pupils with special needs or be a sanatorium school.</p> <p>Schools for pupils with special needs are intended for pupils with physical disabilities, speech impairments, sensory or learning disabilities, or mental disorders, and for pupils who need intervention due to behavioural problems (10.02.1999 entered into force 21.03.1999).</p> <p>Sanatorium schools are intended for pupils with health disorders where pupils study.</p> <p>In the case of special education, arising from a curriculum, the number of academic years may differ from that established in § 2 of this Act. The specific number of academic years, list of subjects and number of lessons in schools for pupils with special needs and sanatorium schools shall be established by a regulation of the Minister of Education (10.02.199 entered into force 21.03.1999).</p>					

FINLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector *		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	543,980		12,490			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	556,470	2007/2008
	352,519	191,461	4,884	7,606		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	44,275 **		- ***			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	44,275 *	2007/2008
	25,407	18,868	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	7,126		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,126	2007/2008
	4,084	3,042	-	-		

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: 'Statistics Finland'.
	14,489		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	9,156	5,333	-	-	14,489	2007/2008	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: 'Statistics Finland'. * 11,809 pupils study full time in mainstream classes (7,830 primary and 3,979 secondary). 10,851 pupils study part of their school day in mainstream classes (4,337 primary and 6,514 secondary). There is no exact data as to the proportion of their school day they study in inclusive settings.
	22,660		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	12,167	10,493	-	-	22,660 *	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	Age 7 to 16 years. The national core curriculum emphasizes the curricular unity of basic education for the whole nine-year period. In grades 1 to 6 pupils are 7 to 13 years old and in grades 7 to 9 they are 14 to 16 years old. Compulsory school age continues until 17 years, if the pupil does not complete basic education before that. Approximately 0.4 % of all pupils repeat a class.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Almost all pupils study in public sector schools and pupils in private schools study according the same national curriculum as pupils in public schools. Almost all private schools get state subsidy.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Basic education is governed by the Basic Education Act (628/1998), the Basic Education Decree (852/1998), the Government Decree on the objectives and time allocation in basic education (1435/2001) and the National Curriculum 2004 given by National Board of Education. Learners have special educational needs when their possibilities for growth, development or learning are decreased by the reason of disability, sickness or decreased working order. Learners with need of psychological or social support or at the risk at these areas have right to support for the learning. Pupils with minor learning or adjustment difficulties have the right to receive part-time special needs education in conjunction with mainstream instruction. If a child cannot cope in mainstream education due to disability, illness, delayed development, emotional disorder or some other similar, he or she may be admitted to special needs education. Special education is provided primarily in conjunction with mainstream instruction or in a special class or at some other appropriate location.						

FRANCE

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	10,040,000		2,598,100			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,638,100	2006/2007
	5,744,500	4,295,500	899,600	1,698,500		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	343,902		- **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	343,902 *	2006/2007
	-	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,097		70,854			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	76,951 *	2006/2007
	4,174	1,923	51,420	19,434		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	160,624		6,812			

	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	37,669	116,143	2,015	4,797	160,624 *	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of National Education (DEPP). * It is not possible to provide separate data for pupils who are fully included in mainstream classes in the public and private sector. However the breakdown of primary and secondary phases across both public and private schools is: primary – 71,399; secondary – 34,928.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	106,327 *	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory school age range is 6 to 16 years. Primary phase is 6 to 11 years and secondary and 11 to 16 years. The legal limits of compulsory schooling are now largely exceeded both in legal texts and in practice. The data refers to pupils in compulsory schools who maybe be aged between 2 to 20 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	The settings created by the Ministry of National Education or by non-profit organisations are, for the most part, financed by public funds. Free education and care are provided in all these settings, segregated or inclusive settings, if they are registered with the proper authorities.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>There is no established term in France which refers to the population of children to who benefit from specific measures defined on the basis of special educational needs: the terms used (disabled children, non-adapted children, which covers different types of situations) are all very specific, linked to certain connotations, and marked by a historical situation.</p> <p>According to the law n° 2005-102 of February 11, 2005 for equal rights and opportunities, participation and citizenship of disabled persons: 'according to the definition of the present law, a disability is constituted by any limit on activity or restriction on the participation in social life endured by a person in his or her environment due to a substantial, durable, or permanent alteration of one or several physical, sensorial, mental, cognitive, or psychic functions, to a multiple disability or to a disabling health problem.'</p> <p>The CDA (Commission on Rights and Autonomy), referring to the list of deficiencies, disabilities and disadvantages (order of January 9, 1989) and to the guide table (decree n° 2008-110 of February 6, 2008) will take a decision on the degree of deficiency and on the educational, therapeutic, material, and human assistance that can be provided to the disabled person.</p> <p>As for children and adolescents recognised as ill, decisions concerning admission to and release from medical institutions are based on a medical decision.</p>						

GERMANY

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	7,871,954		543,269		8,415,223	2006/2007	Source: KMK – Kultusminister- konferenz 2007 documentation of statistics no184 – the information covers the 16 German Bundesländer. http://www.kmk.org/ Federal Statistical Office (2006/2007), general school statistics. * In all data there are figures for pupils who are not allocated by level of schooling. They may be outside the compulsory school age range.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,200,758	Lower Secondary: 4,621,229 Not allocated by level: 49,967	110,527	Lower Secondary: 406,092 Not allocated by level: 26,650 *			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	-		-		479,795 *	2006/2007	Source: Statistische Bundesamt for the KMK. * Data cannot be differentiated between public and private sectors. However the age phase breakdown is as follows: primary: 165,153; secondary: 237,507; not allocated by level: 77,135.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	339,860		67,310		407,170	2006/2007	Source: Statistische Bundesamt for the KMK.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	103,593	Lower Secondary: 186,300 Not allocated by level: 49,967	15,069	Lower Secondary: 25,591 Not allocated by level: 26,650			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream	-		-				* No data is available regarding the numbers of pupils in segregated classes in mainstream schools in any sector or age phase.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistische Bundesamt for the KMK. * Data cannot be differentiated between public and private sectors. However the age phase breakdown is as follows: primary: 46,491; secondary: 25,616; not allocated by level: 518. All Länder provide information on the numbers of pupils fully included in mainstream schools. The proportion of inclusion varies between the Länder.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	72,625 *	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	The duration of full-time compulsory education (compulsory general education) is 9 years (10 years in five of the Länder) and the subsequent period of part-time compulsory education (obligation to attend part-time vocational school) is 3 years. Full-time compulsory education lasts until the age of 16 years, part-time compulsory education lasts until the age of 18 years. Primary age range: 6 to 9 years of age with a theoretical duration of 4 years. Lower secondary age range: 10 to 15 years of age with a theoretical duration of 5 years (6 years in five of the Länder).						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Germany has public and private sector education. Both institutions exist side by side and co-operate with each other. The possibility to establish private schools is guaranteed by the Basic Law. This is combined with a guarantee of the private school as an institution. The constitutional law rules out a state monopoly of education.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	The current definition of special educational needs means specific support for disabled pupils. The area of responsibility of special needs education in the Federal Republic of Germany with respect to all organisational aspects refers to the special needs within the context of disability exclusively. Pupils experiencing problems as a result of certain handicaps and/or in need of additional educational support because of problematic situations, as well as pupils with temporary learning difficulties (e.g. slow learners, reading and writing difficulties) are supported by a combination of measures of differentiation within the structure of the general system of support. Remedial or individual educational programmes based on the general structure, offer and give support for problem situations during the learning process. The Federal Republic of Germany has a comprehensive framework of special measures targeted to additional advice and support for all kinds of situations that might occur in daily school life. NB: the legal definition has to be so wide, because of the different situations and laws in the Länder. Source: KMK – Kultusminister- konferenz: http://www.kmk.org/						

GREECE

Question	Data				Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,134,348		70,369			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,204,717	2007/2008
	734,651	399,697	50,610	19,759		
Pre-primary: 138,606 Primary: 596,045	Secondary: 326,421 TEE: * 73,276	Pre-primary: 4,489 Primary: 46,121	Secondary: 18,297 TEE: * 1,462			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	22,813		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	22,813	2007/2008
	18,155	4,658	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,968		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,968	2007/2008
	3,400	2,568	-	-		
Pre-Primary: 405 Primary: 2,995	Secondary: 322 EEEEK * 2,246					
<p>Source: Ministry of National Education. http://www.ypepth.gr/el_ec_category1823.htm</p> <p>* TEE (Technical Vocational Education TVE) is a very significant sector, not only as an important part of contemporary educational systems in each EU member country, but also as educational units leading to the job market. Pupils with special educational needs may be fully integrated into these schools. From 2008, TEE are transformed to EPAL (Professional Lykeia i.e. high secondary level professional schools, Decision 81646/D4).</p>						
<p>Source: Ministry of National Education</p> <p>* There is no data available concerning the pupils with special educational needs in the private sector. This applies to questions 2 to 5.</p>						
<p>Source: Ministry of National, Education, Department: Information Society. http://www.ypepth.gr/ktp/ktp_amea.htm</p> <p>Pupils attending special pre-primary and primary (177) and secondary schools (10) as well as EEEEEK (71) have been included here.</p> <p>* EEEEEK are public secondary schools offering professional training to pupils with SEN from the age of 12 until 18. Pupils with special needs counted in this section, follow education in special schools during the school day. In the 289 schools of primary and secondary education school programme, curricula and teaching methods are exactly the same with all the state schools.</p>						

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* There are no segregated special classes in mainstream schools, only inclusive classes (see question 5 below).
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	0 *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of National Education, Department of Special Education. * Data from Inclusive classes (former special classes) and from TEE is provided here. Inclusive classes consist of small groups of pupils, operating in all levels of education, at the same mainstream school of the child in addition to the general school programme and providing special teaching (no more than 10 hours per week). These groups may include all pupils who have learning difficulties. Special teaching in language and mathematics is provided by specially trained teachers.
	16,845		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	14,755	2,090	-	-	16,845 *	2007/2008	
	Pre-primary: 651 pupils Primary: 14,104 pupils	Secondary: 1,518 pupils TEE: 572					
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Education in Greece is compulsory for all children 6 to 15 years old; namely, it includes Pre-primary (Nipiagogeio) Primary (Dimotiko) and Lower Secondary (Gymnasio) Education. The school life of the pupils, however, can start from the age of 2 to 5 years in institutions (private and public) called 'Vrefonipiakoi Paidikoi Stathmi' (crèches). In some Vrefonipiakoi Stathmoi there are also Nipiaka Tmimata (nursery classes) which operate along with the Nipiagogeia (kindergartens).</p> <p>Attendance at Pre-primary (Nipiagogeio) lasts for one year. Attendance at Primary Education (Dimotiko) lasts for six years. Children are admitted at the age of 6. In addition to the regular Pre-primary schools (Nipiagogeia) and primary (Dimotika), all-day primary schools are in operation, with an extended timetable and an enriched Curriculum. Along with the mainstream schools of Primary and Secondary Education, Special Pre-primary and Primary schools, Special Gymnasia are in operation, which admit pupils with special educational needs. Musical, Ecclesiastical and Physical Education Gymnasia are also in operation.</p> <p>The Hellenic Compulsory system of education is described at: http://www.ypepth.gr/en_ec_page1531.htm</p> <p>In the mainstream system of National Education, Primary education lasts from 6 to 12 years, secondary education lasts from 12 to 18 years. For pupils studying in school units of Special Education, according to Article 7 of the new law entitled 'School Units of Special Education and Pedagogy' the age range is: for primary education from early childhood until 7; for primary schools until 14, offering extension possibility until 15 of age. For secondary education until 18 offering extension possibility until 23. In the technical/vocational schools, pupils may register after primary schooling in mainstream or special education school for a duration of 5 years. In the EEEK (Laboratories of Special professional education and Training) pupils of mainstream and special schools may register after primary level, upon diagnostic evaluation of the supportive services until the age of 18.</p>						

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public Sector: According to the Hellenic Constitution, all Greek citizens have access to the Greek education system at all levels of public education, as also foreigners under certain conditions. Knowledge of Greek is essential, while at the higher education levels proficiency in a second language is desirable and, in certain circumstances, required. In addition, the system includes intercultural education schools for children with cultural, religious and linguistic particularities. Overall responsibility for education rests with the Ministry of National Education and Religious Affairs.</p> <p>Private sector: primary and secondary schools are under the authority of the Ministry of National Education. Control is mainly exercised in matters of curriculum and competence of teaching staff, as well as financial control in connection with fee collection and increases in fees.</p> <p>http://www.internationaleducationmedia.com/greece/index.htm</p> <p>There are 60 private secondary schools and 150 primary schools. All private schools follow the national state curricula in addition to their extra-curricular activities. At: http://www.ypepth.gr/el_ec_category298.htm</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Several laws were in effect during the last decades in Greece. The Public Law of May 2000, 2817 'Education of children with special educational needs' mandated the free education of children with special needs in kindergarten, elementary, secondary school age children. The structure of the education of individuals with disabilities in Greece as well as the legal definition of Adapted Physical Education is included in this Public Law.</p> <p>According to this Law, education for individuals with special needs is provided in public schools, in special schools and in vocational schools at primary and secondary level. 'Children with special educational needs (SEN) are considered those with increased difficulty in learning and adaptation due to physical, mental, psychological, emotional and social reasons'.</p> <p>Six official categories exist: a) mental retardation, b) sensory-motor disabilities (blind and deaf), c) motor impairments & other health problems, d) speech and language problems, e) learning disabilities and f) emotional disturbances.</p> <p>Education in public schools can be offered in at least 4 settings: a) in mainstream schools, b) in inclusive classes within the public school. In this environment the children with disabilities have to be evaluated, before their entrance, by a group of specialists (elementary school teacher, secondary school teacher, psychologist, medical doctor), c) in special classes within the hospitals/institutions and d) in house.</p> <p>In Greece there are separate public schools for some categories of persons with disabilities. Those are elementary and secondary schools for the deaf, primary and secondary school for the blind, primary and few secondary schools for children with cerebral palsy and severe learning problems.</p> <p>http://www.adapt-europe.org/greece/education.htm</p> <p>The Government presented a new Law to the Parliament with considerable changes in the Special Education framework. This Law has been approved. It is available at: http://www.ypepth.gr/el_ec_home.htm Σχέδιο Νόμου – Ειδική Αγωγή και Εκπαίδευση για τη διασφάλιση ίσων ευκαιριών σε άτομα με αναπηρία και ειδικές εκπαιδευτικές ανάγκες (Draft Law – Special Pedagogy and Education for securing equal opportunities to individuals with disabilities and special educational needs).</p>

HUNGARY

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	1,192,858		130,653		1,323,511	2006/2007	Source: Statistical Yearbook of Education 2006/2007.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	773,528	419,330	56,382	74,271			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	71,122		5,226		76,348	2006/2007	Source: Statistical Yearbook of Education 2006/2007. * Approximately 2,500 pupils are above compulsory school age.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	58,446	12,676 *	3,139	2,087			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	36,930		1,280		38,210	2006/2007	Source: Statistical Yearbook of Education 2006/2007.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	27,845	9,085	463	817			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	-		-		- *	-	* No data is available regarding the numbers of pupils in segregated classes in mainstream schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	34,192		3,946				Source: Statistical Yearbook of Education 2006/2007.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	30,601	3,591	2,676	1,270	38,138	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	5 to 18 years. Primary phase: 6 to 14 years. Secondary phase: 15 to 18 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	The maintainer is the local authority (through the public education) or a Founder, or the Church (by private education). Financial resourcing is the main difference. The financing of public education covers governmental or municipal support directly from the governmental / municipal source (a precise sum/year/student distinct by education level); while private education has the same source, it is given to the maintaining foundations, associations, private persons, or others.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Children/pupils with special educational needs are those who on the basis of the committee of experts on rehabilitation, qualify as suffering from: A) A physical, sensory, intellectual, or speech impairment, autism, or from several of the above mentioned, or from permanent and serious dysfunctions of perceptual functions or behavioural development due to organic reasons; B) Permanent and serious dysfunctions of perceptual functions or behavioural development due to non-organic reasons (as being permanently and seriously hindered in the education and learning process due to disturbances of psychic development, e.g. dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia, abnormal hyperkinesia or abnormal activity disturbance). Reference: Act LXXIX of 1993 on Public Education.						

ICELAND

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Iceland.
	43,875		572				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	30,082	13,793	467	105	44,447	2006/2007	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Iceland. * This total refers to the pupils with the severest needs only (and is the total of questions 3, 4 and 5). These pupils are those covered by the legislation described in question 8. 10,418 pupils – or around 20% of the whole school population – are recognised as having some form of special needs that require additional support, but they are not covered under the legislation. These figures can be broken down as follows: public sector: 10,292 (7,526 primary and 2,766 secondary); private sector: 126 (116 primary and 10 secondary). ** It is not possible to provide a complete breakdown of primary and secondary phases (see note for question 4 below).
	2,145 **		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	0	0	2,145 *	2006/2007	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Iceland. * These pupils are in a special school for pupils with severe learning difficulties.
	160		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	83	77	0	0	160 *	2006/2007	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Iceland. * It is not possible to provide a breakdown of primary and secondary phases.
	384 *		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	-	-	0	0	384	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Iceland. These pupils are all in mainstream schools. There is no information on how many of the pupils getting support in mainstream schools are fully included and how many are in segregated classes within the mainstream school.
	1,601		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,030	571	0	0	1,601	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory age range is 6 to 16 years. (10 years duration). Age 6 to 12 years is the primary phase (7 years duration). Age 13 to 16 years is the secondary phase (3 years duration).						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public sector education is provided completely by the State. Municipalities pay for most of the costs in so called private schools; parents only pay a small amount of the costs.						

8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>There is separate legislation on the affairs of the handicapped (1992) that stipulates that all individuals with handicap (defined as mental retardation, psychiatric illness, physical disability, blindness and/or deafness as well as handicaps resulting from chronic illness and accidents) shall be helped to live and function in a normal community along with other people. For this purpose, where a handicapped person's needs are not covered by general services within the fields of education, health and social services, special services, detailed in the law, shall be provided. The most important legislation that affects the provision of special education is the law concerning compulsory education passed in 1995. The law stipulates ten years of compulsory schooling for children and adolescents between the ages of six and sixteen. The term special education is, however, nowhere to be found in the law. The ideology is that the compulsory 'basic school' shall be inclusive, catering for SEN as well as other educational needs of its pupils. Since 1 August 1996, all compulsory schools, including special schools and units, have been run by local municipalities.</p> <p>One article of the law (article 37) specifies that children and adolescents who need special education because of specific learning difficulties or because they have emotional or social problems and/or are handicapped, have a right to special support in instruction in their studies. The main policy is that such instruction should take place in their local home school. If a pupil's parents or guardians, teachers or other specialists feel that the pupil is not receiving suitable instruction in its home school, the parents or guardians may apply for the pupil to attend a special school. The instruction can be on a one-to-one basis or take place in a group within or outside the mainstream classroom, in special departments within schools or in special schools. A regulation for special education is based on the law. The regulation for special education in compulsory education is the only regulation for this purpose at the four school levels. It deals with all special needs teaching at the compulsory school level. According to this regulation, special education involves changes of educational aims, curricular content and teaching context and/or methods as compared with what other pupils of the same age are offered. Special education is organised on a short- or long-term basis depending on the needs of the pupils, possibly lasting his or her entire schooling. The municipalities are obliged to ensure access to a special school or a special unit for those pupils whose disabilities make it impossible for them to take advantage of educational facilities in their local school.</p> <p>The municipalities are also obliged to offer education for children who are in hospitals or are sick for a long period.</p>
---	---

Inclusive education – Education for All – is the guiding policy for the national education system in Iceland from early years to the transition period. This means addressing and responding to the learning needs of all pupils without treating or defining pupils in need of special support any different from other pupils. In accordance with this there is no separate legislation for special education at any of the four levels of education in Iceland. In short Education for All means that:

- There is equal opportunity for all to attend school and acquire education in accordance with their ability and needs.
- Schools must attend to the ability and needs of all pupils.
- Pupils and/or their parents decide on which school they attend.
- Pupils in need of special support have the right to special provision.

In the school system preschool is considered to be the first education level. A key element of the system is coherence from preschool level to upper secondary school level. New Acts that amongst others strengthen the coherence were adapted in those educational levels in 2008, that is Preschool Act, Compulsory School, Upper Secondary School and higher education. In addition a number of implementing Regulations have been issued providing for various policy details. The Icelandic government has also ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Child (1992) and adopted the Salamanca Declaration (Salamanca 1994) and the Education for All Declaration (Dakar 2000).

References: The law of the handicapped (1995) and the compulsory school act (1995).

The Preschool Act (2008) can be found at http://eng.menntamalaraduneyti.is/media/MRN-pdf/Preschool_Act.pdf

The Compulsory Act (2008) can be found at http://eng.menntamalaraduneyti.is/media/MRN-PDF-Althjodlegt/Compulsory_school_Act.pdf

The Upper Secondary School Act (2008) can be found at

http://eng.menntamalaraduneyti.is/media/MRN-PDF-Althjodlegt/Upper_secondary_school_Act.pdf

IRELAND

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Section of the Department of Education and Science. (All data is/will be available in annual reports). * This breakdown is not available for the private sector. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	631,735		4,692 *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	636,427	2006/2007	
	388,292	243,443	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Section of the Department of Education and Science. * Data is not collected for pupils with special educational needs in mainstream post-primary schools (ages 13 to 16) so they are not included here. There is also a substantial number of pupils with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes in mainstream primary schools for whom data is not available. ** These pupils are of compulsory school age. In addition there are 2,574 pupils above compulsory school age in the compulsory sector.
	13,490		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	13,490 **	2006/2007	
	13,490	- *	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Section of the Department of Education and Science. * These figures refer only to pupils in special schools. Data are not collected in regard to pupils in special classes in mainstream settings. ** Special schools in Ireland are designated primary schools only, but do have pupils above compulsory age and some special schools provide 'senior cycles' to such pupils. There are 1,256 pupils above compulsory school age in such schools.
	5,322 **		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,322 *	2006/2007	
	5,322	-	-	-			

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Section of the Department of Education and Science. * It is not possible to provide separate information for 4 and 5 (see note below).
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Section of the Department of Education and Science. * The figures refer to pupils with SEN in mainstream schools and they cover special classes and mainstream classes. The figures are not differentiated. ** There are 1,318 pupils with SEN above compulsory school age in mainstream settings.
	8,168 **		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	8,168 *	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory schooling covers age six to sixteen years, or completion of three years in a post-primary school. Primary school pupils range on average in age from 5/6 to 12/13 years and secondary school pupils range on average in age from 12/13 to 17/18 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public schools are grant-aided by the state. Private sector education is funded mainly by parents. Private schools do not receive funding from the state.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	'Special educational needs' means, in relation to a person, a restriction in the capacity of the person to participate in and benefit from education on account of an enduring physical, sensory, mental health or learning disability, or any other condition which results in a person learning differently from a person without that condition.' Reference: Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act 2004.						

ITALY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,775,620		550,947			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,326,567	2007/2008
	2,579,959	4,195,661 Lower secondary: 1,625,651 Upper secondary: 2,570,010	254,746	296,201 Lower secondary: 103,392 Upper secondary: 192,809		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	162,266		8,430			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	170,696	2007/2008
	65,190	97,076	4,346	4,084 Lower secondary: 2,526 Upper secondary: 1,558		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector **		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	693		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		

Source: Ministry of Education data
www.pubblica.istruzione.it
'Editoria' Title of Publication:
'La scuola statale: sintesi dei dati a.s. 2007/2008'
(Public school: collection of data)
Private sector source of data: 'Notiziario Statistico – a.s. 2007/2008' this publication is on the web site of Ministry of Education
www.pubblica.istruzione.it

Source: www.pubblica.istruzione.it (see question 1).

Source: www.pubblica.istruzione.it
* Segregated settings do not exist, except schools for pupils who are blind or deaf. These are:
primary: 1 school for pupils who are deaf and 1 school for pupils who are blind; lower secondary: 3 schools for pupils who are deaf; upper secondary: 3 schools for pupils who are deaf and 1 school for pupils who are blind.
** There are no pupils in private sector segregated settings.

	62	631 Lower secondary: 186 Upper secondary: 445	0	0	693 *	2007/2008	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* In public and private schools, there are no special, segregated classes.
	0		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	0 *	-	
	0	0	0	0			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: www.pubblica.istruzione.it
	161,573		8,430				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	65,128	96,445 Lower secondary: 54,032 Upper secondary: 42,413	4,346	4,084 Lower secondary: 2,526 Upper secondary: 1,558	170,003	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	With the last law on education n. 53 dated on 28/3/2003, pupils have a right to education for 12 years. Compulsory age starts from 6 and ends at 18 years old. Education is free of charge until the end of lower secondary education. At the end of the three years of lower secondary education, pupils can choose between upper secondary education (with charges and books on their family, but the didactical areas and staff school dependents by state) or training education (a mixed managing between state and regions). At the moment, the two branches of secondary education, upper secondary education and training education, are changing and it will be necessary for further legislation for the re-structuring of internal organisation, the government and didactical issues. Primary school is from 6 to 11 and secondary school (including lower – three years of schooling – and upper secondary – five years of schooling) from 11 to 18/19.						

7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>Public schools are funded by the State: the internal staff school (teachers, headmasters and administrative assistants) is selected by national public entrance examination and all of them dependents of the State.</p> <p>All schools (primary, lower and upper secondary) are obliged to follow the national guide on education and they are visited periodically by Inspectors. A sub-category of public school is the 'scuola paritaria': a school legally recognised, mix in funding by privates and state, the school staff is selected directly by school and depends on it. This type of school is obliged to follow the national guide on education. To have a legal status of 'school' (this means: to be officially recognised), the institution is obliged to accept the enrolment of pupils with SEN.</p> <p>Private schools are funded only by private sectors as parents, associations, charities etc. The staff school is selected and paid by the school management. They are not obliged to include pupils with SEN in the classrooms.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The legal definition of 'people with disabilities' is enshrined within the Act n. 104, dated on 5/2/1992 that sets the picture of who is a person with disabilities. A 'person with disabilities' is anyone who presents a physical, psychological, sensory impairment, permanent or progressive, that causes a learning, social, working difficulty and that causes a situation of disadvantage or social marginalisation.</p> <p>The Act is value also and without discrimination for foreigners, stateless, domiciled or resident people inside the borders of the national territory.</p> <p>The Act assures the right of people with disabilities to education at pre-primary schools (not compulsory), in integrated settings of each grade of compulsory education (primary, lower and upper education) and at university.</p> <p>The Act states: 'Scholastic inclusion aims to develop the potentiality of the person with disabilities in learning, in communication, in relationships, in social life. The right of education cannot be limited by learning difficulties or problems caused by disabilities and handicaps. The recognition of 'person with disabilities' leads to the drawing up of the documents related to functional diagnosis useful to formulate the personal educational plan, a draft of work developed via co-operation between the parents of the pupil, the health care personnel and, for each grade of education, the support teachers of the school where the pupil is enrolled. The profile indicates the physical, psychical and social-sensitive peculiarities of the pupil and it highlights both the learning difficulties caused by the handicapping situation and the means of addressing them, the qualities that the pupil has at the moment and how to support, stimulate, develop and them within a perspective of respect for the cultural choices of the person with disabilities.'</p> <p>The Presidential decree dated on 19.5.2006 states that the medical commission appointed to release the statement/certificate of disability have to refer to international indicators pointed out by OMS – IC10.</p>

LATVIA

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	198,049		- *		198,049	2007/2008	Source: All data for questions 1 to 5 is taken from the statistics report of the Ministry of Education and Science. * In the report there is no official data about private sector in education. This applies to questions 1 to 5. The report also lacks data about those pupils of compulsory school age who receive their education in part time schools or so called 'evening schools'. The data is available on the web site: www.izm.gov.lv
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	117,084	80,965	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	8,535		-		8,535 *	2007/2008	Source: Statistical report of the Ministry of Education and Science. * No pupils above compulsory school age are included in the data provided.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	5,244	3,291	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	6,857		- *		6,857	2007/2008	Source: Statistical report of the Ministry of Education and Science. * The available data is only about children with SEN in special schools and special classes in public schools, there is no data about children with SEN in private schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,948	2,909	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	1,026		-		1,026	2007/2008	Source: Statistical report of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	818	208	-	-			

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Annual statistics reports from schools the situation at the beginning of the school year available in the Ministry of Education and Science. * At this point the official data is about pupils with SEN in inclusive settings where an appropriate special education programme is licensed. There are many more children with SEN in inclusive settings who receive support measures, but they are not reflected in the official data of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	652		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	478	174	-	-	652 *	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	Basic education is compulsory in Latvia and covers from the age of 7 to 16 (9 years: 1 st to 9 th grade), but it is possible to acquire basic education to the age of 18 (Law of Education, article 4, 1999). Basically it is possible can call 1 st to 6 th grade (ages 7 to 13) primary education and 7 th to 9 th grade (ages 14 to 16) lower secondary education, but officially these levels are not recognised in legislation.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	According to the Law of Education, Article 23 (1999): (1) State educational institutions are founded, re-organised or closed by the Cabinet of Ministers following the motion of the Minister of Education and Science or the Minister of other fields. (2) Municipality educational institutions are founded, re-organised or closed by municipalities conforming to the Ministry of Education and Science, or the Ministry of respective field and the Ministry of Education and Science. (3) Private educational institutions are founded, re-organised and closed by juridical person or private person. State and municipalities may take part in the foundation of private institutions. (4) Foreign juridical persons may found, re-organise or close educational institutions in accordance of this law and other law, as well as with international agreements.						
7. Legal Definition of SEN	Law of Education, Article 1, paragraph 24 states that Special Education is available for persons with SEN and health impairments or it can be an adapted general or vocational education for persons with SEN and health impairments. The Regulations of the Cabinet of Ministers Nr. 579 of October 21, 2003 lists diagnoses of impairments and suggested educational curricula according to which a person can acquire his/her education. These regulations cover a wide spectrum of impairments and provisions the institutions should provide for a person with SEN.						

LITHUANIA

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	511,306		3,356 **		514,662 *	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education and Science, Department of Statistics. * For pupils who have severe and profound dysfunctions it is compulsory to be in the education system in Lithuania, until the age of age 21 years. This is outlined in the new version of the Law on Education. These pupils have been included in data for questions 1 to 5. ** A primary secondary breakdown of data from the private sector is not available.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	139,276	372,030	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	58,603		35		58,638 *	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education and Science, Centre of Information Technologies of Education. *Pupils from grade 0 to grade 12 only are covered.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	29,897	28,706	16	19			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	6,045		35 **		6,080 *	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education and Science, Centre of Information Technologies of Education * Pupils from grade 0 to grade 12 only are covered in this data. ** Complete data for pupils with SEN included in mainstream settings in private schools is not available. These figures are for a private special school. This is the only such school in Lithuania at the moment.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,451	4,594	16	19			
4. Pupils with SEN in	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of	Source: Ministry of Education and Science, Centre of Information Technologies of Education.

	224		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	51	173	-	-	224	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education and Science, Department of Statistics. * Pupils from grade 0 to grade 12 only are covered in this data. ** No data is available for pupils with SEN in private mainstream settings.
	52,334		- **				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	32,674	19,660	-	-	52,334 *	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory education in Lithuania is 6/7 to 18 years. For pupils with severe and profound dysfunctions, it can be 6/7 to 21 years of age. Primary schooling is 6/7 to 10 years (4 years). Lower secondary schooling is 10 to 16 years (6 years). Upper secondary schooling is 16 to 18 (2 years).						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Republic of Lithuania Law on Education (2003) Article. 18: A school is considered to be private if a legal or physical body is its founder; if a Lithuanian legal or physical body together with foreign legal or physical body is a founder of a school; if a foreign legal or physical body is a founder. Any ministry, municipality, county administration, the Parliament, Government cannot be a founder of a private school.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Special Educational Needs means the need for assistance and services arising from the fact that the mainstream educational and self-educational requirements do not correspond with the opportunities of pupils with special needs. Reference: Republic of Lithuania Law on Education (2003).						

LUXEMBOURG

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	57,540		2,358		59,898	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. www.men.public.lu
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	42,734	14,806	200	2,158			
	Pre-primary: 10,001 Primary: 32,733						
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	1,375		3		1,378 *	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg and SREA (service responsible for pupils with SEN included in mainstream schools). * This data includes 43 pupils above compulsory school age.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,141	234	1	2			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	728		0		728	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	554	174	0	0			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	-		-		- *	-	* Separate data is not available, as these pupils are considered to be on the roll of special schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: SREA (service responsible for pupils with SEN included into mainstream schools).
	647		3				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	482	165	1	2			
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education in Luxembourg covers 11 years: two years of pre-primary school (4 to 6 years), six years of primary school (6 to 12 years) and the first three years of secondary school (12 to 15 years). 1 year of non-compulsory school is offered to children aged 3 to 4 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	The Luxembourg State is in charge of organising and controlling the educational system. Public and private schools teach the same topics. In Luxembourg most primary and secondary schools are public schools. Public education is free of charge. Private schools are nearly all catholic schools and are not free of charge. Private schools in these figures are grant-aided schools. Non grant-aided international schools are not listed in these statistics. 6,420 pupils attend these schools.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Law of Special Education of 1973: 'The Government makes sure, that every child because of his mental, sensory, emotional or motor particularities gets the instruction required by his state or situation in structures of Special Education.' Law of 1993 states that the named children can be included in ordinary schools.						

MALTA

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education of Malta.
	32,355		20,195				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	16,031	16,324	10,307	9,888	52,550	2007/2008	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education of Malta.
	1,770		617				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,211	559	342	275	2,387	2007/2008	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education of Malta. * In Special Schools there is no primary and secondary age phase.
	289 *		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	0	0	289	2007/2008	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education of Malta. * There is only one special class in one primary school on the island of Gozo.
	18 *		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	18	0	0	0	18	2007/2008	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education of Malta.
	1,463		617				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	904	559	342	275	2,080	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	For mainstream settings compulsory school age is from 5 to 16 years. In special schools there is a concession to keep pupils up to the age of 19 years. Pupils of age range between 5 to 11 years attend primary schools and pupils of age range between 11+ to 16 years attend secondary schools.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public sector education is where pupils attend educational provision provided by the State. Public sector education is free. Private sector education (also called non-state education) includes Church Schools and Independent Schools. Parents of children attending Church Schools do not pay tuition fees. These are subsidised by the State as per an agreement between the Government of Malta and the Church. On the other hand, parents who send their children to independent schools pay fees. There are no segregated special schools in the private education sector.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	'A minor shall be deemed to have special educational needs when that minor has special difficulties of physical, sensory, intellectual or psychological nature.' Article 45 (2), Education Act, as emended in 2006, Chapter 327 of the Laws of Malta.						

NETHERLANDS

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	2,403,113		- **		2,403,113 *	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education. * The number of pupils in all the answers has increased significantly since the previous data collection exercise, due to a change in legislation. As of 2006, compulsory education covers the age range 5 to 18 years. ** No data is available on pupils in private education. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,427,819	975,294	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	88,295		-		88,295	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	55,256	33,039	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	59,176		-		59,176 *	2006/2007	Source: Ministry of Education. * In addition to this total, as of 1/10/06 1,367 pupils aged 19 or over were in full time education.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	34,385	24,791	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	-		-				* No data is available regarding numbers of pupils in segregated classes in mainstream schools.

	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education.
	29,119		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	20,871	8,248	-	-	29,119	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory schooling is from 5 to 18 years. This is a change since previous data collection exercises – the compulsory schooling period has been extended. Primary schooling is from 4 to 12 years of age. Secondary schooling is from 12 to 18 years of age.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Private schools do not receive any funding from the Government. No data is available on pupils in private education.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	The law on the Expertise Centres (WEC 2003) states that pupils are eligible for special education if they meet certain criteria. These are largely based on existing practice. Criteria is as follows: for pupils with a visual impairment, it is a visual acuity of <0.3 or a visual field that is < 30 and limited participation in education as a result of the visual impairment. For pupils with a hearing impairment, it is a hearing loss > 80 dB (or for hard of hearing pupils 35 to 80 dB) and limited participation in education are required. The decision to provide extra funding for pupils with a learning disability (mentally handicapped) will be based largely on IQ < 60. For physically impaired and chronically ill pupils medical data showing diagnosed disabilities/illness are required. The criteria for behaviourally disturbed pupils require diagnoses in terms of categories of the DSM-IV, problems at school, at home and in the community and a limited participation in education as a result of the behaviour problems.						

NORWAY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	619,322		15,202			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	634,524	2007/2008
	430,099	189,223	9,449	5,753		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	34,518		804			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	35,322	2007/2008
	22,489	12,029	536	268		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,083		88			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,171 *	2007/2008
	866	1,217	36	52		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	32,435		716			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		

Source: Compulsory School Statistics (GSI).

Source: Compulsory School Statistics (GSI).

Source: Compulsory School Statistics (GSI).
* The number of pupils with SEN in segregated settings is according to the GSI-data. There is some uncertainty related to this data as all segregated settings may not be accounted for in official statistics.

* No data is available for this question.

Source: Compulsory School Statistics (GSI).

	21,623	10,812	477	239	33,151	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory school age range is 6 to 16 years (10 years of schooling). Primary school: 6 to 12 years of age. Secondary school: 13 to 16 years of age.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Private schools are regarded primarily as a supplement to local authority schools. Most private schools are run by religious denominations or by organisations representing specific views of life or alternative educational approaches. Some offer essential instruction that the local authority schools are unable to provide. Authorised private schools receive financial support from the State. Legal definition: Section 2–12 (Education Act). Private primary and lower secondary schools. The Ministry must approve private primary and lower secondary schools. Approval shall be granted when a school fulfils the requirements laid in the Act relating to primary and secondary education especially when it comes to curriculum, assessment and the organisation of the pupils learning environment. Persons who run private primary and lower secondary schools without such approval are liable to fines. In the case of foreign and international primary and lower secondary schools in Norway, the Ministry may grant exemptions from the requirements.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Right to special education: pupils who either do not or are unable to benefit satisfactorily from ordinary tuition have the right to special education. In assessing what kind of tuition shall be provided, particular emphasis shall be placed on the pupil's developmental prospects. The content of the courses offered shall be such that the pupil receives adequate benefit from the tuition as a whole in relation to other pupils and in relation to educational objectives that are realistic for the pupil. Pupils who receive special education shall have the same total number of teaching hours as other pupils. Expert assessment: before the municipality or the county authority takes a decision concerning special education or a decision concerning special educational assistance an expert assessment shall be made of the pupil's specific needs. This assessment shall determine whether the pupil needs special education, and what kind of tuition should be provided. The expert assessment shall consider and determine the following – the pupil's benefit from ordinary tuition, learning difficulties the pupil has and other special conditions of importance to tuition, realistic educational objectives for the pupil, whether it is possible to provide help for the pupil's difficulties within the ordinary educational provisions and what kind of tuition it is appropriate to provide. The Ministry may issue further regulations concerning expert assessment. If the decision of the municipality or county authority differs from the expert assessment, it shall be explained in the grounds for the decision why the municipality or county authority is of the opinion that the tuition received by the pupil fulfils the pupil's rights. Reference: Education Act No. 5						

POLAND

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	5,673,987 *		121,885 *		5,795,872	2007/2008	Source: Ministry of National Education. * Exact data is not available for the breakdown of pupils in primary and secondary sectors in both the public and private sectors. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	- *		- *		167,783 **	2007/2008	Source: Ministry of National Education. * Data is collected in all compulsory schools without the division for public and non-public schools. There is incomplete data available about pupils with SEN in public and non-public mainstream settings. ** No data is available for how many pupils with SEN above compulsory school age are in the compulsory sector.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	88,888		2,135		91,023	2007/2008	Source: Ministry of National Education.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	-		-		- *	-	* No data is available relating to the numbers of pupils with SEN in special classes in mainstream schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
6. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	*		*				Source: Ministry of National Education. * Data is collected in all compulsory schools without the division for public and non-public schools. There is no separate data available
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	-	-	-	-	76,760	2007/2008	
5. Compulsory age phase	<p>Education begins at 6 years of age and is compulsory until the age of 18 years. Primary schooling is from 6 up to 13 (for pupils with SEN it can be 2 more years – this means up to 15 years). Secondary schooling is from 13 up to 16 (for pupils with SEN it can be 2 more years – means 18 years). For pupils with SEN compulsory education must be finished no later than when they are 21 years old (approximately).</p>						
6. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>In line with the Education Act of 1991, schools can be public and non-public. A public school is an educational institution established by the central administration, local/district/regional authorities, other legal body or by an individual person. It provides free education and implements the core curricula and assessment procedures established by the relevant minister of education. A non-public school is an educational institution run by the legal bodies or individual persons on the basis of their incorporation into the register of non-public schools. Non-public schools are financed within the framework of a general subsidy from the State Budget and additionally by fees received from parents and funds. Non-public schools in Poland have the right to issue school certificates that are recognised by all other schools and by the universities. Most non-public schools have small numbers of pupils and small classes.</p>						
7. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Special Needs Education (SNE) concerns children and youths with developmental disabilities who require special organisation of work, working methods and special equipment. It can take place in general schools, integration schools/classes, or special schools/classes. Special Education covers the following groups of pupils with special educational needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pupils with slight mental disability; - Pupils with moderate and severe mental disability; - Pupils with profound mental disability; - Deaf pupils; - Pupils with hearing impairment; - Blind pupils; - Pupils with visual impairment; - Pupils with physical disabilities; - Chronically ill pupils; - Pupils with psychiatric problems; - Autistic pupils and pupils with multiply disability; - Pupils with social and behavioural problems; - Pupils with speaking and communication problems. <p>SNE is regulated by the Act on School Education of 7 September 1991, with further amendments and the resolution of Minister of National Education about special needs education. All pupils with SEN receive the assistance from Psychological and Educational Services Centres free of charge and on the voluntary basis. Results of psychological, pedagogical and medical assessment serve as a basis for qualifying pupils for suitable forms of education (general schools, integration schools, special schools) although the final decision is up to the parents.</p>						

PORTUGAL

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	1,110,637		124,827		1,235,464	2006/2007	Source: School Census. 2006/2007, GEPE, Ministry of Education.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	468,765	641,872	49,089	75,738			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	41,171		3,576 *		44,747	2006/2007	Source: DGIDC (Innovation and Curricular Development Department), Ministry of Education. * Complete data for pupils in all sectors in private education is not available. These figures are a summation of what data is available for questions 3, 4 and 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	19,642	21,529	3,576	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	- *		3,576		3,576	2006/2007	Source: DGIDC. * There are no public special schools in Portugal.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	3,576	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	1,336		- *		1,336	2006/2007	Source: DGIDC. * No data is available.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,336	- *	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	39,835		- *				Source: DGIDC * No data is available.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	18,306	21,529	-	-	39,835	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education covers 6 to 15 years of age. Primary phase age ranges from 6 to 9 years of age. Secondary phase age ranges from 10 to 15 years of age.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	The data above refers to private special schools funded by the State.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Definition of SEN: children and young people receiving special education because they have difficulties in their learning process and participation in education, considering the interaction between inter-related factors and limitations in their functioning. Source: DGIDC Direcção-Geral de Inovação e de Desenvolvimento Curricular (Innovation and Curricular Development Department), Ministry of Education.						

SLOVENIA

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	257,566		- *		257,566	2007/2008	Source: Statistics Base; Ministry of Education and Sport. * No data is available for pupils in the private sector. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	165,910	91,656	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	9,446		-		9,446 *	2007/2008	Source: Statistics Base; Ministry of Education and Sport. * The data includes pupils in mainstream schools, special schools and institutions for learning disabilities and schools for deaf, blind mobility impaired and pupils with emotional and behaviour problems.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	9,446	1,649	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	1,597		-		1,597 *	2007/2008	Source: Statistics Base; Ministry of Education and Sport. * The data includes pupils in special schools and special institutions for pupils with learning difficulties and in schools for pupils who are deaf, blind, mobility impaired and pupils with emotional and behaviour problems.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,597	-	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	370		-		370 *	2007/2008	Source: Statistics Base; Ministry of Education and Sport. * This data refers to pupils with learning disabilities in special classes in mainstream schools.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	370	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	7,479		-				Source: Statistics Base; Ministry of Education and Sport.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	7,479	-	-	-	7,479	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	In Slovenia only primary education is compulsory. Compulsory education is from 6 to 15 years old (9 years duration). Pupils who are included in adapted programmes of education for blind and visual impairment, deaf and hearing impairment, speech and language difficulties, physically impaired and pupils with learning difficulties can stay in schools until age 18 years. Pupils with SEN in adapted and special educational programme can stay in the school 3 or 6 years longer. After ages 18 or 21 they can go into adapted employment or daily employment and social centres.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Private schools are not a part of the public educational system. Their status makes them distinct from those schools that operate on the basis of concession agreements and their programmes do not differ from programmes of public schools. The expression 'private schools' also includes private schools, which carry out their educational programmes according to the internationally valid pedagogical principles (Steiner, Freinet, Decroly, Montessori etc.).						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	In the legalisation the following groups of pupils are identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Children with mental disabilities;- Children who are blind or have visual impairment;- Children who are deaf or hard of hearing;- Children with speech and language problems;- Physical disabled children;- Long-term illness children;- Children with learning difficulties and- Children with emotional and behaviour problems. Reference: The Placement of Children with Special Needs Act (2000, 2007).						

SPAIN

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,918,306		1,454,412			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,372,718	2006/2007
	1,702,246	1,216,060	835,787	618,625		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	80,528		31,419			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	111,947	2006/2007
	51,450	29,078	18,134	13,285		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	14,030		12,448			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	26,478	2006/2007
	9,625	4,405	8,099	4,349		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	-	-
	-	-	-	-		
<p>* The Statistical office does not provide this data. There are pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools for two reasons: there is no segregated special school near the rural area; the segregated special school has not got vacancies and pupils have to be educated in a mainstream school. Please note: these pupils are considered pupils with SEN in segregated special schools so they are included in the data given for question 3 above.</p>						

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Social Politics and Sports, Statistical Office.
	66,498		18,971				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	41,825	24,673	10,035	8,936	85,469	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education is from 6 to 16 years. Compulsory primary education is from 6 to 12 years. Compulsory secondary education is from 12 to 16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>Public education: educational settings belong to the State. All the funding (including teachers' salary – they are civil servants) is provided by the State. Public education is totally free of charge. The majority of the Spanish pupils/students are educated in this sector.</p> <p>Private education: the ownership of private educational establishments is held by a private naturalised or legal person. These private establishments may subscribe to agreements with the Administration, in which case they are known as subsidised private schools. Parents pay for private education.</p>						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>This definition is taken from the Organic Act (see reference below). Within this law, SEN is included as one of the three categories of pupils with specific educational support needs. These are: pupils with special educational needs; high ability pupils; late entries into the education system. Pupils with special educational needs refers to those who require certain support and specific educational attention due to disability or serious behavioural disorders, either for a period or throughout the whole of their schooling. It is the responsibility of the Education Administrations to guarantee and regulate the schooling of these children and ensure the participation of parents or guardians in the decisions which affect the schooling and educational procedures of these pupils. It is also their responsibility to adopt the appropriate measures to provide parents of these children with adequate individual assessment and the necessary information to help them in the education of their children.</p> <p>The schooling of pupils with special educational need is governed by principles of normalisation and inclusion and ensures non-discrimination and real equality in the access to the education system and continued attendance, allowing flexibility in the different stages of their education when necessary. The schooling of these pupils in special education centres or units, which may be extended to the age of 21, only takes place when their needs cannot be met by the special needs provision available in normal schools. The identification and assessment of the educational needs of these pupils will be carried out as early as possible by qualified professionals, under the conditions determined by the Education Administrations. At the end of each school year the results obtained by each student are assessed, according to the objectives set in the initial assessment. This will allow staff to provide appropriate guidance and adapt the learning programme in order to encourage, as far as possible, better integration of these pupils.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the Education Administrations to provide infant school provision for children with special educational needs and to develop appropriate schooling programmes for them in primary and secondary schools. It is also the responsibility of the Education Administrations to encourage pupils with special educational needs to continue with post-compulsory education as appropriate and to modify as necessary the testing procedures established in this Law for those pupils with disabilities.</p> <p>Pupils with special educational needs can attend both special education and mainstream establishments. Schooling should preferably be provided in mainstream establishments, adapting such programmes to each pupil's capacities.</p> <p>References: LOE: Título II, Capítulo I, Sección primera: Alumnado que presenta necesidades educativas especiales. LOE: Organic Law of Education. Ministry of Education and Culture, 3rd May 2006. Title 2, Chapter I: Pupils/students with Specific Need of Educational Support.</p>						

SWEDEN

Question	Data				Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector			
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	849,664		86,205		935,869 *	Source: Database of the Swedish National Agency for Education. * A breakdown of pupils in primary and secondary phases in each of the public and private sectors is not available. This applies to questions 1 to 5. However, the breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: primary – 279,721; secondary – 656,148.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	-	-	-	-		
	2007/2008					
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	13,878 **		520 **		14,398 *	Source: Database of the Swedish National Agency for Education * These pupils have cognitive disabilities who are enrolled in the special programmes and pupils who attend a state school for the deaf. The breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: primary – 2,904; secondary – 11,494. This figure includes 1,108 pupils above compulsory school age.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	-	-	-	-		
	2007/2008					
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	514 *		0		514	Source: Swedish National Agency for Education. *These pupils attend a state school for the deaf pupils. ** This figure includes 70 pupils above compulsory school age.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	103	411 **	-	-		
	2007/2008					
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	13,364 *		520 *			Source: Swedish National Agency for Education. * These figures cover pupils with cognitive disabilities who are enrolled in the special programmes. These programmes are offered in every municipality and pupils are more or less included in the mainstream school. ** The breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: primary – 2,801;
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		

	-	-	-	-	13,884 **	2007/2008	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* In Sweden, there is an unknown number of pupils with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes. Data is not collected relating to these pupils.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory age phase is 7 to 16 years. Primary age phase is 7 to 9 years. Secondary age phase is 10 to 16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Private schools in Sweden are called Independent Schools. They are open to everyone and free of charge. The municipality where the student lives pay the school a per student, per year grant.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Please refer to notes above for a clear indication of which pupils the data refers to.</p> <p>There is no legal definition of SEN. In Sweden education follows the principle of 'a school for all' and the focus is on what kind of support the student needs.</p> <p>The basic principle guiding all Swedish education is 'a school for all' – access to equivalent education for all. This means that pupils in need of special support should not be treated or defined as a group that is any different from other pupils and their rights are not stated separately. The obligation for schools to attend to all pupils' needs is, however, emphasised.</p> <p>Pupils in need of special support have the right to specialist provision. All education corresponds as far as possible to the National curricular, but with the emphasis upon meeting individual learning needs. In a few circumstances, this provision is offered in special settings. Special schools with sign language communication are available for pupils with severe hearing impairments.</p> <p>All pupils have the right to choose their school – either municipal or independent – as long as it can demonstrate that that school meets the pupils' educational needs.</p> <p>Reference: All information is taken from Swedish school law and National curriculum documents, e.g. Education Act (1985:1100) Ch.1. General Provisions, Curriculum for the Pre-school Lpfo 98, Curriculum for the Compulsory School System, the Pre-School Class and the Leisure-time Centre Lpo 94, Curriculum for the Non-Compulsory School System Lpf 94.</p>						

SWITZERLAND

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	755,981		41,882				Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	489,491	266,490	21,313	20,569	797,863	2006/2007	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	34,523		11,860				Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office. * Complete data is not available as the data concerning question 2 is not available in Switzerland for 2006/07. Pupils included in mainstream classes are statistically lost due to the current data collection scheme (based on classes not individual data). The figures listed here represent pupils in special schools and special classes in mainstream schools (i.e. the data presented for questions 3 and 4 below).
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	46,383 *	2006/2007	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	6,092		10,044				Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office. * This data refers to pupils in special schools with an 'official recognition' of SEN.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,553	2,539	5,771	4,273	16,136 *	2006/2007	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	28,431		1,816				Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office. * This data refers to pupils with learning difficulties, behavioural problems in special classes in mainstream schools. These pupils are recognised as having SEN under cantonal legislations; however, they do not fall under the national definition of SEN.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	18,296	10,135	922	894	30,247 *	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	This data is not collected in the 26 Swiss cantons at present. Pupils integrated in mainstream classes are statistically lost due to the current data collection scheme (based on classes not individual data).
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	-	-	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education is from 4 to 17 years. Primary education is from 4 to 12 years and secondary from 13 to 17 years.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public schools are fully funded by the government; the private sector includes schools with public subsidies or no subsidies.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Individuals entitled to benefits: Children and youth from birth to 20 years of age, living in Switzerland, have the right to adequate provision of special educational services, provided the following conditions are met:</p> <p>a. Prior to compulsory education: if it can be established that the development is limited or at risk or that without specific support following instruction in regular classrooms will not be possible;</p> <p>b. During compulsory education: if it can be established that possibilities of development and education are limited in such a manner that instruction in regular classrooms cannot be followed without specific support any more or if other special educational needs are established.</p> <p>Art 3. Inter-cantonal Agreement of Collaboration in the Domain of Special Needs Education, 25th October 2007. (Interkantonale Vereinbarung über die Zusammenarbeit im Bereich der Sonderpädagogik vom 25. Oktober 2007).</p>						

UNITED KINGDOM (ENGLAND)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	7,397,250		667,446		8,064,696 *	2007/2008	Source: Department for Children, Schools and Families (DCSF). SFR 15/2008 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2008 (Table 1a). * For all data, it is not possible to give an exact primary/secondary school split. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	215,910		11,750		227,660 *	2007/2008	Source: DCSF. SFR 15/2008 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2008 (Table 1a). * The following notes apply to all data presented in questions 2 to 5: - All data covers pupils with statements only. - It is not possible to say how many pupils are above compulsory school age as published data on pupils with statements does not allow for the removal of either pupils with statements in nursery classes (under the age of 5) within primary phase schools (either mainstream or special), or pupils with statements over the age of 16 in secondary phase schools (either mainstream or special). This is explained in question 5. - It is not possible to say across all sectors whether pupils are in primary or secondary phases. - The data has been rounded up to the nearest 10.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	82,470		11,750				Source: DCSF. SFR 15/2008 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2008 (Table 2). * This figure is for all pupils in some form of segregated school. The breakdown is: in the public sector maintained special schools (including foundation schools) 82,470; in the private sector non-maintained special schools 3,590, independent special schools 6,620, and other independent schools 1,540.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	-	-	-	-	94,220 *	2007/2008	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	<p>Source: DCSF. SFR 15/2008 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2008 (Table 2).</p> <p>* This figure is for all pupils in some form of segregated class in a mainstream school. The breakdown is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resourced provision/special classes in maintained mainstream schools – 9,070 - SEN units in maintained mainstream schools – 7,820 <p>However it should be noted that it is not possible to say to what degree pupils are segregated or included. This varies from provision to provision.</p> <p>** No data is available.</p>
	16,890 *		- **				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	16,890 *	2007/2008	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	<p>Source: DCSF SFR 20/2007 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2008 (Table 2).</p> <p>Please Note that these figures are calculated on a very crude indicator (i.e. enrolment at a mainstream or non-mainstream school). Some pupils on roll in mainstream schools may be in segregated classes while some pupils on the roll of special schools may spend the majority of the week in a mainstream classroom. More accurate data on actual practice is not available at the national level.</p> <p>* This figure is for all pupils in fully inclusive settings. The breakdown is: maintained mainstream schools (including foundation schools) – 111,210; pupil referral units – 2,040; hospital schools – 130; academies – 1,690; pupils who are excluded and where other arrangements are made for them – 1,480.</p> <p>** There are 2,150 pupils who are either awaiting placement or their parents have made alternative arrangements for them. It is not possible to indicate where they are educated and they are not included in these figures.</p>
	116,550 *		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	116,550 **	2007/2008	

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The compulsory school age range is 5 to 16 years. However, published data on pupils with statements does not allow for the removal of either pupils with statements in nursery classes (under the age of 5) within primary phase schools (either mainstream or special), or pupils with statements over the age of 16 in secondary phase schools (either mainstream or special). Data presented above includes these populations. Primary education begins in the year a child is 5 years old and continues until they are 11. Compulsory secondary education is from 11 to 16 years.</p>
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>‘Private education’ is that which is provided in institutions, which are largely privately funded, receiving most of their income from tuition fees. There is private provision at all levels of education. Private schools are known as independent schools and they do not receive direct government funding, although some independent schools have charitable status and benefit from tax relief and they may also apply for some public support through, for example, the National Lottery funding scheme.</p> <p>All independent/private schools must meet regulatory requirements (Sections 463-478 of the Education Act 1996), which include reaching satisfactory standards of premises, accommodation, instruction and staffing. They must be registered with the Department for Education and Skills (or national equivalent) and are subject to regular inspection from Her Majesty’s Inspectors to ensure their fitness to be registered.</p> <p>* Note: included pupils of all ages in schools, excluded pupils in maintained and direct grant nursery schools.</p> <p>While they are not required to follow the national curriculum, independent/private schools must offer a curriculum of sufficient range and depth to be appropriate for the age, aptitude, ability and special educational needs of the pupils placed there.</p> <p>Non-maintained special schools (NMSS) are schools in England approved by the Secretary of State for Education as special schools that are not maintained by the state, but charge fees on a non-profit-making basis. Most non-maintained special schools are run by major charities or charitable trusts. It should be noted that most places in NMSS are purchased by local authorities for pupils for whom there is no available appropriate provision in a maintained school: parents rarely pay fees directly in these schools.</p>

8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The Education Act 1996 (as amended by the Special Educational Needs and Disability Act – SENDA, 2001) for England and Wales, and the Education (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 for Northern Ireland, states that a child has special educational needs ‘if s/he has a learning difficulty which calls for special educational provision to be made for her/him’. Such provision is required when a child:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Has significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of children of his/her age; or- Has a disability which either prevents or hinders him/her from making use of educational facilities of a kind generally provided in schools, within the area of the local authority concerned, for children of his/her age; or,- Is under the age of five years and is, or would be if special educational provision were not made for him/her, likely to fall within either of the above paragraphs when over that age. <p>The Education Act 1996 (as amended by SENDA 2001) defines special educational provision as provision which, in the case of children over the age of two, adds to or differs from provision made generally for pupils of the same age in maintained schools. Pupils cannot be defined as having special educational needs solely because their mother tongue is not English or because they are gifted.</p> <p>The revised Code of Practice (DfES, 2001) recommends a graduated approach to meeting children’s special educational needs. A first step would be ‘School Action’: the school (or early years centre) should meet children’s SEN out of its own resources; at ‘School Action Plus’ (or Early Years Action Plus) the school will mainly meet children’s SEN out of its own resources, but with some help from outside the school, for example advice from an educational psychologist. If parents or the school feel that a child’s needs cannot be met without extra resources they can ask the local authority to carry out a statutory assessment of a child’s SEN. If the local authority feels it is necessary to carry out an assessment it must do so and, again if necessary, issue a statement of special educational needs setting out a child’s SEN and the provision to meet those needs. The local authority must then arrange that educational provision.</p>
-----------------------------------	---

UNITED KINGDOM (SCOTLAND)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	649,132		30,519 *		679,651	2006/2007	Source: the Scottish Government, Pupils in Scotland 2006, Statistical Bulletin and Independent School Census. This includes all pupils. * All data for pupils in private education includes pupils outside the compulsory school age range. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	385,710	263,422	11,697	18,822			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	33,823		3,503		37,326 *	2006/2007	Source: the Scottish Government, Pupils in Scotland 2006, Statistical Bulletin and Independent School Census. * In Scotland the concept of Additional Support Needs (ASN) is used. Please see question 8 below for a full definition.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	18,912	14,911	1,031	2,472			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	5,878		1,103		6,981	2006/2007	Source: the Scottish Government, Pupils in Scotland 2006, Statistical Bulletin and Independent School Census.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	2,974	2,904	121	982			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	2,124		0		2,124	2006/2007	Source: the Scottish Government, Pupils in Scotland 2006, Statistical Bulletin and Independent School Census.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,316	808	0	0			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	25,821		2,400				Source: the Scottish Government, Pupils in Scotland 2006, Statistical Bulletin and Independent School Census.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	14,622	11,199	910	1,490	28,221	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The usual arrangements for pupils entering the first class of primary school are that children whose 5th birthday falls between the start of March and the end of February start school together in the August in the middle of that period. However, parents may choose to defer entry. Pupils who reach the age of 16 between 1 March and 30 September of a given year can leave that summer, or if they reach 16 from 1 October to the following end of February can leave at the end of the winter term during that period.</p> <p>Public sector: Primary phase pupils are pupils aged 4 or older in primary schools or pupils aged 4 to 11 years in special schools. Secondary phase pupils are pupils in secondary schools aged under 16 or pupils aged 12 to 15 years in special schools. Ages are as at 30th September 2006.</p> <p>Private sector: Primary phase pupils above are in primary schools or are pupils under 12 in special schools. Secondary phase pupils are pupils in secondary schools or pupils aged 12 or over in special schools. Ages at 31st December 2006.</p>						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	<p>Publicly funded schools are local authority and grant-aided schools. A grant-aided school is a school in receipt of funding from the Scottish Government.</p>						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Definition of Additional Support Needs (ASN) in The Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004:</p> <p>(1) A child or young person has additional support needs for the purposes of this Act where, for whatever reason, the child or young person is, or is likely to be, unable without the provision of additional support to benefit from school education provided or to be provided for the child or young person.</p> <p>(2) In subsection (1), the reference to school education includes, in particular, such education directed to the development of the personality, talents and mental and physical abilities of the child or young person to their fullest potential.</p> <p>(3) In this Act, 'additional support' means:</p> <p>(a) in relation to a prescribed pre-school child, a child of school age or a young person receiving school education, provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally for children or, as the case may be, young persons of the same age in schools (other than special schools) under the management of the education authority for the area to which the child or young person belongs;</p> <p>(b) in relation to a child under school age other than a prescribed pre-school child, such educational provision as is appropriate in the circumstances.</p>						

UNITED KINGDOM (WALES)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	388,304 *		7,164 **		395,468	2006/2007	Source: Schools in Wales General Statistics 2007. * Public sector data collection covers primary and secondary education and special schools. For special schools, there is no primary secondary age split available. ** Data is not available regarding the split of the private sector into primary and secondary age phases. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	13,290 **		462 **		13,752 *	2006/2007	Source: Schools in Wales General Statistics 2007. * The data in this section is based only on those pupils with SEN who have a Statement of Special Educational Needs. See question 8 below for definition of Special Educational Needs. ** Data provided in this section includes primary, secondary and special schools as well as pupil referral units. Private sector data includes independent schools and 'education otherwise' (i.e. mainly pupils educated at home).
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	2,987 *		- **		2,987	2006/2007	Source: Schools in Wales General Statistics 2007. * Data is not available regarding the split into primary and secondary age phases in special schools. ** No data is available to show segregated settings within Independent Schools (Private Sector).
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	2,906 *		- **				Source: Schools in Wales General Statistics 2007. * Data is not available regarding the split into primary and secondary age phases in special classes in mainstream schools. ** No data is available to show the segregated settings within Independent Schools (Private
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			

	-	-	-	-	2,906	2006/2007	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Schools in Wales General Statistics 2007. * Data is not available regarding the split into primary and secondary age phases in fully inclusive settings.
	7,397 *		462				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	7,859	2006/2007	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory school age is classed as pupils aged 5 to 15 years of age. Data collection is completed for the following 3 categories: under 5 years, 5 to 15 years and 16 years and over. It is not split into primary and secondary in most cases.						
7. Clarification of Public – Private sector education	Public sector education – education which is controlled by the Government Private sector education – education which is not controlled, but the Government or Local Education Authorities and run privately.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Children have special educational needs if they have a learning difficulty that calls for special educational provision to be made for them. Children have a learning difficulty if they: a) Have a significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of children of the same age; or b) Have a disability which prevents or hinders them from making use of educational facility of a kind generally provided for children of the same age in schools within the area of the local education authority; c) Are under compulsory school age and fall within the definition at (a) or (b) above or would so do if special educational provision was not made for them. Special educational provision means: a) For children of two or over, educational provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally for children of their age in schools maintained by the LEA, other than special schools, in the area. b) For children under two, educational provision of any kind. SEN Code of Practice for Wales 2002.						